

ISic3691

I.Sicily inscription 3691

Language

Ancient Greek

Type**Material****Object****Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of Vigna Cassia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329593

1. [— —]NOC.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 329593

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 04.0024bis

Orsi, P. 1923. Manipulus epigraphicus christianus memoriae aeternae I.B. de Rossi dicatus. Contributi alla Siracusa sotterranea. *Atti della Pontificia Accademia Romana di Archeologia. Memorie*. 1: 113-122. At no.25

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